

CHARACTERISTICS OF METHODOLOGY FOR PEDAGOGICAL WORKS OF DIFFERENT GENRES FOR 1ST CLASS STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article outlines thoughts and opinions on the methodology of reading stories, fairy tales and other genres of literary genres. In particular, in elementary grades, the main types of work include explaining the content of the story, working with a dictionary, and retelling the text read.

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА МЕТОДИКИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ РАЗНЫХ ЖАНРОВ УЧАЩИМСЯ 1-ГО КЛАССА

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ABSTRACT

В данной статье изложены мысли и мнения о методике чтения рассказов, сказок и других жанров о литературных жанрах. В частности, в начальных классах к основным видам работы относятся объяснение содержания рассказа, работа со словарем, пересказ прочитанного текста.

1-SINF O'QUVCHILARIGA HAR XIL JANRDAGI ASARLARNI O'RGATISH METODIKASINING XUSUSIYATLARI

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vosita, g'oyani eshitish.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada adabiy janrlar haqida hikoyani, ertakni va boshqa janrlarni oqish metodikasi haqida fikr va mulohazalar keltirib o'tilgan. Jumladan, boshlangich sinflarda hikoyani o'qishga bag'ishlangan izohli lug'at darslarida o'qilgan hikoya mazmunini ochish, lug'at ustida ishlash, o'qilgan matnni qayta hikoyalash asosiy ish turlaridan hisoblanadi.

Introduction. Stories, poems, fairy tales, parables, proverbs and riddles are studied practically in the primary classes. In addition to them, scientific and popular articles are also taught. Artistic works of different genres have their own characteristics due to the construction and stylistic receptions, and their impact on students is also different. Accordingly, when reading works of art of different genres, the teacher is required to choose appropriate methods.

A story is a small artistic work, in which a certain event in a person's life is described by summarizing the important aspects of life. "A story often describes an episode in a person's life. Its content is more vital than that of a fairy tale."

Opening the contents of the story, working on the dictionary, and retelling the read text are the main types of work in the explanatory dictionary classes dedicated to reading the story in primary grades. The content of the story is usually analyzed based on questions. The questions will be aimed at analyzing the behavior and character of the participant. Companions are used for two purposes: to analyze the content of the story and to compare facts, opinions, conclusions, to identify and generalize connections between events and actions.

Theoretical Basis. In the lesson of reading a story, it is important to explain the meaning of words and phrases that students do not understand, so they cannot understand the content of the story. Without spending a lot of time explaining the meaning of the word, it is explained by giving a short explanation of the word that is most necessary for understanding the content of the work. Analyzing the content of the story and developing students' speech on this basis takes a special place in reading the story. After the story is read, students should be given time to think and express their opinions. The purpose of the first questions asked about the read work is to find out whether the children liked the idea, which of the characters in it influenced the child, who or what the children want to tell a story about. Only after that, questions are used

that help to reveal the plot of the story, the direction of the story, to understand the character of the characters, and finally to find out the main idea of the work.

When analyzing a work of art, it is important to focus on the full explanation of the plot, and the participants should not ignore such types of work as characterization, construction of the work, and analysis of the language.

The questions are usually asked by the teacher, but it is very useful to ask the students questions about the content of the work and the behavior of the participants. This method is very popular with children and enlivens the work; it helps students to understand the content of the work well, acquire the skills to express their thoughts coherently, and fully remember the connection between the content and the events.

In the process of working with the text, in order for the students to master the story well, learn the idea presented in it, read selectively, answer questions, make up a question for the story part, draw a picture with words and graphics, make a plan, all types of retelling, types of work such as preparation for expressive reading are used.

The following plan scheme is taken into account when organizing a lesson on interpretive reading of a short fiction story:

1) preparation for reading the story, the life of the people described in the story, a short description...);

2) expressive reading of the story (complete or logically completed parts) by the teacher or a pre-prepared student;

3) a short conversation about the behavior of the participants in the perception test, the relationship between people and events

4) re-read the story (divide the story into parts, teach students, explain the meaning of some words);

5) conduct a conversation about each section of the story and find a title; planning a story;

6) expressive reading of some parts of the story;

7) retelling based on the plan;

8) preparation for expressive reading or dramatization of the story (in the classroom or at home);

9) expressive reading of the story and expressive retelling.

This story reading lesson is a variation of the plan and is subject to change. However, it should not be forgotten that in the lesson of reading an artistic story, along with knowing its content and main idea, the educational effect of the work (education of students in the example of a work of art), especially the aesthetic effect is also taken into account, and great importance is attached to expressive retelling.

A fairy tale is the most common genre in folklore, in which ordinary events and fantastic adventures in people's lives are told. In many fairy tales, the image of real life is combined with fantastic elements.

Elementary school students will be introduced to the fairy tale in practice. The exciting plot of the fairy tale, the extraordinary and wonderful situation in the development of the story will fascinate children; brave, strong, resourceful, brave, agile characters, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, the constant victory of good power - goodness in it attracts children.

The form of storytelling adopted in a fairy tale, repetition of the same words and phrases over and over again, melodiousness, impressiveness of language, liveliness of means of expression are very interesting for children. Participants in the fairy tale are often divided into compassionate, generous, fair, and their opposites, evil, miserly, and greedy.

The pedagogic value of the fairy tale is that children are happy that righteousness and honesty won in it, that poor people got rid of difficulties, that is, that good and goodness came true, and that evil and evil were condemned. They always want it to be like this in life. The fairy tale develops children's ability to evaluate the behavior of the characters by discussing them. What qualities in people did you like in the process of analyzing the story? What for? ... why was it punished (or encouraged)? Why are some characters in the fairy tale helped even by the forces of nature, and some, on the contrary, turned away? they think to answer such questions, discuss the behavior of the heroes of the fairy tale and learn to evaluate it. For example, the main idea in the fairy tale "Ur Tokmok" is to express the return of good and the condemnation of evil, while in the fairy tale "Donishmand" it is to encourage harmony.

In a fairy tale, people tell their own lives, therefore, by reading a fairy tale, students learn about the life, thoughts and dreams of the people of a certain period. The fairy tale is also of great importance in developing students' speech. The fairy tale provides the necessary material for developing connected speech in the text. Young students read the fairy tale with great interest. They tell vividly, preserving the figurative expressions and visual means, as well as the unique syntactic structure of the tale, the structure of the sentence.

In primary grades, stories about animals are taught more often. Anvar Obidjon's fairy tales such as "Bo'ring tabib bo'lgani haqida ertak", "Ko'zacha bilan Tulki", "Olapar, Mosh, Musicha" are taught and analyzed in the style of real-life stories. When working with the text, such types of work are used as selective reading, answering questions, making up and answering questions by students themselves, drawing graphic pictures with words, making a plan, retelling stories, and telling stories. In these tales, the habits of animals are analyzed, but it is not recommended to compare them with the character of people.

In addition to fairy tales about animals, elementary school students also read fairy tales such as "Davlat", "Tuz xaqi", "Ovchi, Kukcha va Dono", "Ilm afzal". Preparing students for reading such fairy tales is similar to preparing them for reading scientific and popular texts (observation, excursion, subject lessons), reading and analyzing the fairy tale is organized in the style of an artistic story.

When working on a fairy tale, it is important to teach children not only to read a fairy tale, but also to tell it. Telling stories develops oral speech, enriches children's speech with new words and phrases, and cultivates love for the mother tongue.

In order to teach the free use of fairy tale language in the 1st grade, the teacher can tell it (if the fairy tale is not large) during the first introduction to the fairy tale. Taking into account the above, the construction of the lesson of reading the fairy tale with interpretation can be as follows:

- 1) preparing students to understand the fairy tale;
- 2) teacher's expressive reading and recitation of the fairy tale;
- 3) conducting a short interview to determine how well the students understood the story;

4) read and analyze the fairy tale in parts; to find some visual means, synonyms, to explain the meaning of some words;

5) preparing to tell a story (reading inside);

6) telling a story;

7) summarizing conversation (opening the idea of a fairy tale);

8) retell the story with a certain task;

9) check and complete the task. (Why did we read the fairy tale with interest?)

10) preparing to read (or tell) a fairy tale at home to interest others.

Conclusion. Above, thoughts and comments about the methodology of teaching stories, fairy tales and other artistic genres about literary genres were given. In particular, it was said that revealing the content of the read story, working on the dictionary, and retelling the read text are considered to be the main types of work in the explanatory dictionary classes dedicated to reading stories held in primary grades.

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